

Environmental Scan Summary

The following provides an overview of neighbourhood assets and potential barriers/gaps for older adults. The features were identified through a structured assessment in March 2019. As such, this summary should be viewed as an overview of key features observed rather than an exhaustive list.

Macassa appears to be an older neighbourhood that is mainly residential. Most houses in the neighbourhood are bungalows. Toys were seen strewn across some lawns, suggesting the neighbourhood is comprised of young families. There are apartment buildings along major streets such as Mohawk Road and Fennell Ave E. Snow was shoveled from sidewalks, and garbage and recycling were well maintained. From the few people observed on the streets and in stores, the population appears predominantly Caucasian. Most services, restaurants, and grocery stores were located on the large streets which serve as neighbourhood boundaries.

There were a few places of worship scattered throughout the neighbourhood. Macassa has two large parks - Macassa Park and Vincent Massey Park. Macassa Lodge is a long-term care facility located in the neighbourhood that runs an adult day program. A few health services were observed, however it appeared that the services were not geographically distributed throughout the neighbourhood. There was only one small plaza with a medical clinic, pharmacy, physiotherapist, orthotics and counselling services, and a wellness centre.

One of the most notable attributes is the neighbourhood's cleanliness - little to no garbage was observed along the sidewalks and lawns. Also, many of the roads and sidewalks are very wide and wheelchair accessible. However, there is a substantial lack of important services. For example, one of the larger grocery stores -No Frills- has recently closed. Also, many of the health services are localized to a single plaza, which decreases accessibility to such services for residents who live farther away. For older adults, distance may be a barrier to these services, discouraging some individuals from accessing them when needed.

Rebecca Ganann | ganann@mcmaster.ca
Caroline Moore | camoore@mcmaster.ca

Sihota D., Tandon M., Nadarajah A., Wang A., and De Panfilis L. on behalf of the EMBOLDEN research team (2019). Environmental scan: Macassa. URL: <https://emboldenstudy.mcmaster.ca/projects-results/>

Index of services in Macassa

Map Number	Description
Education	
1	Blessed Sacrament Catholic Elementary School
2	Newcombe House Secondary School
Fitness/Recreation	
3	Mt Hamilton Youth Soccer Club
Food Sources	
4	Dairy Queen Grill and Chill
5	Jeow Hot Sauce
6	Joni's Pizza
7	Tim Hortons
Health/Social Services	
8	Macassa Lodge*
9	The Orthotics Place
10	Your Inner Solutions
Housing	
11	El Mirador Apartments
12	Skyview Hawk Apartments
Parks	
13	Macassa Park
14	Vincent Massey Park
Protective Services	
15	Hamilton Fire Department Station 4
Religious Centres	

16	Community of Christ
17	Japanese United Church
18	Most Blessed Sacrament Roman Catholic Church
19	Reorganized Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints
20	St. Thomas Chaldean
Stores	
21	99 Cent Store
22	Food Basics
23	Goldie's Variety
24	RBC Royal Bank
25	Speedy Auto Service Hamilton Mountain
26	Sports Swappers
27	Trade My Wheels
28	Walmart

*Programs Targeted Specifically at older adults

Environmental Scan Update, 2022

The neighbourhood's programs and services appeared consistent with those available for the community in the initial environmental scan completed in 2019. For instance, the initial environmental scan identified 26 relevant services across various categories; presently, 26 services have also been identified though the distribution of services has varied across the two time points. Minor changes are seen in the number of services across service categories in education, health/social services, religious centres, and stores (Table 1). These changes can be attributed to services no longer being operational due to COVID-19-related closures and other operational status changes (e.g., changes in management, location changes, etc.). For example, Newcombe House Secondary School (education services), Reorganized Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints (religious services), 99 Cent Store (retail store), and Trade My Wheels (retail store) have been permanently closed. Additionally, healthcare services such as Your Inner Solutions, which provides marriage, couples and relationship counselling services, operate in Burlington with a satellite office in Hamilton currently.

In terms of newly identified services, Dentistry on 7th, Seven Star Medical Centre & Pharmacy, Hamilton Speech Services, and Hamilton Massage Therapy were all services newly identified within the health/social services category. They support various social and health needs in the community. For instance, Dentistry on 7th provides dental services in the neighbourhood and the Seven Star Medical Centre & Pharmacy provides a range of health services including general pharmacy services and educational consultations to review complex prescriptions with a pharmacist. Hamilton Speech Services provides speech and language interventions to children and youth and Hamilton Massage Therapy provides a range of massage therapy options.

The COVID-19 pandemic had varying degrees of impact on service delivery within the community. More specifically, among all the identified services in 2022 the largest proportion remain open and serve the community in person. This is followed by services that are closed (either permanently or temporarily) and services that are provided through online options, because of public safety concerns. Services with unclear operational statuses (i.e., services categorized as “unclear status (with an attempt to

contact)” in Table 1) follow these two categories and require further follow-up to verify the status of their operation. Table 2 provides a detailed list of services within the Macassa neighbourhood and their current operational status (as impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic).

Table 1. Number of Services Identified and COVID-19 related status

	Number of Services (2019)	Number of Services (2022)	Open, in-person	Open with online options available	Unclear status	Closed
Education	2	1	1			
Fitness/ Recreation	1	1	1			
Food Sources	4	4	3		1	
Health/Social Services	3	7	6	1		
Housing	2	2	2		1	
Parks	2	2	2			
Protective Services	1	1	1		1	
Religious Centres	5	4	2		2	1
Stores	6	4	4			2
Transportation	0	0	0			
Total	26	26	22	3	2	3

Table 2. Summary of Services COVID-19 Status and Function

Open, in-person (with modified procedures for public safety)	Open with online options available	Unclear status (with attempt to contact)	Closed
Education			
Blessed Sacrament Catholic Elementary School			Newcombe House Secondary School ¹
Fitness/Recreation			
Mt Hamilton Youth Soccer Club			
Food Sources			
Dairy Queen Grill and Chill La Vera Pizza ² Tim Hortons		Jeow Hot	
Health/Social Services			
Macassa Lodge The Orthotics Place Dentistry on 7 th Seven Star Medical Centre & Pharmacy Hamilton Speech Services Hamilton Massage Therapy	Your Inner Solutions ³		
Housing			
El Mirador Apartments Skyview Hawk Apartments			
Parks			
Macassa Park Vincent Massey Park			
Protective Services			
Hamilton Fire Department, Station 4			

¹ Newcombe House Secondary School is permanently closed.

² La Vera Pizza was previously operational under the name “Joni’s Pizza”.

³ Your Inner Solution operates in Burlington with a satellite office in Hamilton.

Open, in-person (with modified procedures for public safety)	Open with online options available	Unclear status (with attempt to contact)	Closed
Religious Centres			
Community of Christ Most Blessed Sacrament Roman Catholic Church		Japanese United Church St. Thomas Chaldean	Reorganized Church of Jesus Christ of Latter- Day Saints ⁴
Stores			
Goldies Variety RBC Royal Bank Speedy Auto Service Hamilton Mountain Sports Swappers			99 Cent Store ⁵ Trade My Wheels ⁶

⁴ Reorganized Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints is permanently closed.

⁵ Cent Store is permanently closed.

⁶Trade My Wheels is permanently closed.

Rebecca Ganann | ganann@mcmaster.ca
Caroline Moore | camoore@mcmaster.ca

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CT Highlights

Population
= 2,584

Number of Homes
= 1,131

Population Density
= 3,220/Km²

5-year Population change
= 2.0%

Age Distribution by Gender

\$39,760
Average Income
(after tax)

10.0%
Unemployment
Rate

Citizenship & Immigrant Population

Canadian Citizens

Immigrants Recent Immigrants

Language Spoken at Home

English | 89.1%
Non-official Languages | 8.3%

Highest Certificate, Diploma or Degree

No certificate, diploma or degree
Secondary (high) school diploma or equivalency
Postsecondary certificate, diploma or degree

Neighbourhood Homes

\$1,332 (own)
 \$1,140 (rent)

Average monthly shelter costs

39%
Rent their home

\$606,000
Average home value

20%
Apartment > 5 stories

94%
Built before 1980

6%
Major repair needed

Public Health
Agency of Canada

Agence de la santé
publique du Canada

Rebecca Ganann | ganann@mcmaster.ca
Caroline Moore | camoore@mcmaster.ca

Data Source Statistics Canada. 20215370008.00 [Census tract].
www.statcan.gc.ca

Cite

Siddiqui, S., Orr, E., Ganann, R. On behalf of the EMBOLDEN research team. (2023).
Infographic: Neighbourhood Profile Macassa
URL: <https://emboldenstudy.mcmaster.ca/projects/results/>